

Authentic Materials for Developing Productive and Receptive Pronunciation Skills

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Abstract: *In this paper, I provide a rationale for using authentic materials in the pronunciation classroom, focusing on how they can be used to develop both the receptive and productive skills of English language learners. For improving productive skills, authentic native speaker (NS) speech samples are presented to draw learner attention to suprasegmentals, an underrepresented area in EFL pronunciation instruction, and to develop pronunciation intelligibility. For improving receptive and accommodation skills, authentic samples of non-native speaker (NNS) Englishes are presented to direct learners to unfamiliar features of English pronunciations they are likely to encounter in lingua franca use. Supporting activities, outlining how both NS and NNS Englishes can be exploited to improve language skills and familiarize students with 'real' English, are also provided.*

Introduction

This paper will explore using a range of authentic materials for pronunciation instruction. I will argue that authentic materials are superior to the use of didactic materials, especially with regard to awareness and production of suprasegmentals. Though segmentals should still be a significant feature of comprehensive pronunciation instruction, there is now widespread agreement that suprasegmentals play an increasingly vital role in improving the intelligibility of language learners. Recent research highlights this need for greater focus on suprasegmentals (Koike, 2014; Diaz, 2017). Additionally, in a world with an ever-growing population of NNSs (Crystal, 2008), teachers must go beyond the confines of NS Englishes when dealing with pronunciation instruction. In both EFL and ESL contexts, students stand to benefit from exposure to NNS Englishes (Jenkins, 2000; Walker, 2010) which should also be presented to learners in the form of authentic materials. In response to this exponential growth of NNSs and the use of English as a lingua franca, I will outline the advantages to learners of such exposure and highlight resources for classroom use.

Authentic Materials Defined

There are wide and varied definitions of the term “authentic” as it relates to materials for classroom use. Porter and Roberts (1981) first defined authentic materials as those “not intended for non-native learners” (p. 37), and Nunan (1989) similarly regards them as “any material which has not been produced for the purpose of language teaching” (p. 54). While literature on authenticity has more recently highlighted the complexities of defining authenticity and authentic materials (see Gilmore, 2007), I will focus on the definitions above for the purposes of this paper; that is, to maintain the highest degree of authenticity, materials must be intended for a native speaker audience. I will also introduce the idea that authenticity should ideally involve spontaneity in order to fully display the suprasegmental features of speech which are the target language focus of the NS speech samples. For example, speech samples from interview data on the International Dialects of English Archive (IDEA) site are an excellent resource for the study of suprasegmentals, as the spontaneous nature of interviews lends itself to an abundance of these target features.

Suprasegmentals and Authentic Materials

Many teachers would be aware of the term “textbook English” and there is a reason for its existence. With the intention of including target grammar or vocabulary in short conversations and to scaffold learning for lower-level English Language Learners (ELLs), it is often deemed necessary to create unnatural-sounding samples to make the target language more accessible. While this is understandable on the part of those who create EFL pedagogical materials and may be helpful in the initial stages of language learning for teachers and students, it leaves the learner ill prepared for an environment where such language is non-existent. Such an environment may be any place where English is used naturally between NSs or NNSs. It is essential that students, especially those of intermediate or advanced levels, are provided with authentic samples of speech when giving pronunciation instruction to prepare them for the real world of English. The first and most important reason for this is because authentic materials are rich in suprasegmental features that the often-contrived listening materials of textbooks, or the clearly spoken language teacher, avoids. Celce-Murcia et al. (2010) cite Barrerre’s (2007) research on authentic nurse-patient interaction, noting that it can be used to practice pausing, prominence and intonation. Celce-Murcia et al. also point out, when discussing connected speech, that the “overarticulated” speech of ESL and EFL listening material may be responsible for the development of “listening and speaking skills based on false premises” (p. 175). Levis and Levis (2010) highlighted how authentic materials and academic lectures in their study were efficient in displaying sentence stress, where in 90 percent of all utterances, final content words required stress. They state: “The authentic texts we examined show many examples of this, and these kinds of texts are severely underrepresented in pronunciation teaching materials” (p. 143). In addition, Aufderhaar (2004), in a study using authentic audio text such as radio plays intended for a native speaker audience, made findings that reinforce the abundance of suprasegmentals found in authentic material. Out of the 24 students in the study, 14 reported increased awareness of suprasegmentals such as stress, intonation and linking after listening to the audio texts.

The Benefits of Studying Suprasegmentals for Pronunciation

Having established that authentic materials are indeed richer in suprasegmentals, it is important to consider how this can be of benefit to English language learners. There is an established line of research that supports the effectiveness of focusing on suprasegmental aspects of English when teaching pronunciation. Hahn (2004) observed reactions to NN primary stress when it was (a) Correct (b) Incorrect and (c) Absent. Upon listening to the correct sentence stress, it was found that evaluation by raters was higher and that more content was retained. The overall conclusion was that correctly placed stress positively affects intelligibility. Derwing et al. (1997) found positive results in an experiment consisting of 13 non-native speakers (NNS) enrolled in 12 weeks of instruction where the focus was more on suprasegmental features rather than segmentals. The participants made progress in at least one of the three areas they were judged on (accent, intelligibility, comprehensibility). Also, in another research project examining the benefits of suprasegmentals, Derwing et al. (1998) tested three groups that were instructed differently and found evidence supporting suprasegmental instruction as the most effective. One group was instructed in segmentals, another in suprasegmentals, while the third received no pronunciation instruction. The only group that displayed improvement with unrehearsed speech was the group that received instruction on suprasegmentals. The issue of suprasegmentals being neglected in pronunciation pedagogy is another factor to consider. Due to the greater traditional focus on segmentals and the deficiency in suprasegmental instruction, it is still clearly an area lacking in attention in the student's language learning experience. As Derwing (2003) notes in a study of one hundred ESL students, "the relatively low numbers of participants who nominated prosodic factors as the cause of communication problems may reflect a lack of awareness of prosodic issues, perhaps because these are rarely taught" (p. 559).

NNS Englishes and Authentic Materials

Additionally, the use of authentic materials in English language classes is extremely important to familiarize students with a variety of not only NS accents but also NNS Englishes. With English as the undisputed global lingua franca and with exponentially more NNSs than NSs, unsurprisingly, among the total sum of interactions in English around the world today, those involving only NSs now represent a clear minority (Graddol, 2006). As a result, there has been much discussion as to which model is the most appropriate for pronunciation instruction, whether it be a NS model such as Received Pronunciation (RP) or North American English (NAE), or Jenkins' lingua franca core (LFC). Although a case can be made that the native speaker model is more appropriate for activities requiring the production of language such as mirroring, described later in this paper, for the purposes of improving receptive skills, inclusion of NNS Englishes has become a necessary component of English language instruction. Inclusion of NNS Englishes still appears to be far from the norm, however. In an examination of six government-approved textbooks for Japanese junior high schools, Sugimoto and Uchida (2016) discovered that, despite the characters in the listening material coming from a variety of backgrounds, of a total of 50 characters, 46 had North American accents and the remaining four were also NSs. Though recent textbooks provide a greater range of NS accents, the authentic materials that I will introduce in this paper provide a more valuable and wide-ranging source of NNS Englishes. IDEA, for example, which is one of the primary resources

for language analysis activities described later in this paper, includes a total of 1,520 speech samples, the majority of which are NNS samples.

The Benefits of Exposure to NNS Englishes

The benefits of exposure to NNS varieties of English are twofold. Firstly, through exposure to accents outside of the normal range of NS accents offered in standard English textbooks, greater exposure to previously unfamiliar Englishes can be achieved. This is especially important when there are particular NNS Englishes that a student is likely to come into contact with based on their world region. For example, in the Japanese context, such as the one I teach in, it would be beneficial to expose the students to NNS Englishes from the same region such as Chinese or Korean Englishes, as there is a greater likelihood of students encountering English speakers from these countries. Jenkins (2000), in listing the conditions for “receptive convergence” notes it is necessary “the receiver has had prior exposure to the speaker’s accent” and “the receiver has had prior exposure to a range of L2 accents and has developed a tolerance of difference” (p. 183). She also notes that the best way to achieve this familiarity is through “repeated pedagogic exposure” (p. 184).

The second important benefit of exposure to NNS Englishes is learner confidence and acceptance of one’s own form of English as a legitimate World English variety. There are students who when exposed exclusively to NS English may encounter feelings of discouragement for what seems an unattainable goal; that of native-like pronunciation. Introducing NNS Englishes into the classroom can present the idea that there are many World Englishes, of which each student is a speaker and each of which is legitimate. In an interview on her attitudes to ELF and learning English, a Taiwanese English teacher, although expressing a desire to strive higher, expressed “comfort” at knowing the level of a native English speaker was not required (Holliday, 2005). Also, in a project involving online communication between Taiwanese and Japanese students (Ke & Suzuki, 2011), many students commented on gains in their “confidence” or “not being afraid” leading the authors to posit that “NNS-NNS communication may be a good choice, particularly for those learners with low self-confidence” (p. 185).

Autonomous Learning, Motivation and Authentic Materials

Although not the focus of this paper, there are other benefits to using authentic materials that warrant mention, in the form of autonomy and motivation. As the materials I will introduce are freely available on the Internet, these resources are easily accessible at all times at no cost to the students allowing a degree of learner autonomy. This is in contrast to more traditional resources where the teacher is generally the only class member with access to the educational materials used in class, for example in the form of a CD or cassette. Students who choose to repeat exercises conducted in the classroom as an extra-curricular activity have the ability to do so with Internet-based materials. Activities such as identifying suprasegmental features and shadow reading can easily be continued outside the classroom without the supervision or instruction that a teacher usually provides. Also, TED talks and YouTube, which are the two primary sources for finding subjects for activities such as mirroring, are sites that are already familiar to most students. Research also indicates that authentic materials have a positive impact on the motivation levels of language

learners. Peacock (1997), in a study of adult beginner-level students at a South Korean university, noted that levels of on-task behavior increased, as did concentration when using authentic materials as opposed to using “artificial materials”. Also, in a study by Wu et al. (2011) of Taiwanese and international students, positive attitudes towards aural authentic materials were observed with “drama” and “TV program” scoring highly in ratings of preference, with low scores for textbooks.

Pronunciation Materials and How to Use Them

The International Dialects of English Archive (IDEA) is an invaluable resource for exposing students to a wide range of NNS Englishes. The original intention of the site was to provide actors with real-life models for their characters, not as a language teaching resource. There are approximately 1,500 speech samples from 120 countries and territories. All of the speech samples begin with a scripted sample, either the passage *Comma Gets a Cure* or *The Rainbow Passage*, which are of great benefit for making comparisons of the features of differing Englishes but, due to being scripted, rates lower as an authentic source of speech for the purposes of pronunciation instruction. However, these are followed by a sample of extemporaneous speech that has both an orthographic transcription and, in a number of samples, a phonetic transcription. The Speech Accent Archive is a similar site, containing almost 3,000 NS and NNS speech samples of a set text. As with IDEA, it also has a “Generalizations” section that highlights the phonetic features of each accent.

Activity 1: Identifying Suprasegmental Features (Production)

Speech samples from IDEA are ideal for making students aware of several different suprasegmental features that contribute to NS speech. Listening activities that require students in pairs or groups to identify suprasegmental features, and then present their findings to the class, help students develop an awareness of these features. As the NS samples are richer in suprasegmental features, I use these for this activity. In order for students to be able to identify suprasegmental features in awareness activities, it is necessary to first provide the students with some background knowledge of suprasegmentals. Unlike segmentals, with which many students of English will have had some exposure, instruction in suprasegmentals is less common and therefore familiarization is important. Features that can be readily identified by students after a short lecture describing suprasegmentals are (a) lexical and nuclear stress (b) intonation (rising and falling pitch) and (c) connected speech. For this activity, students are instructed to transcribe the speech samples, writing stressed words in capital letters and drawing intonation contours. “California 10”, as a representative North American accent, is suitable for a first-time lesson, as it is an accent familiar to most students (each speech sample is categorized with a region and number). Students should be able to recognize the subject’s sentence stress, with stress being focused on the main verbs and nouns with no emphasis on the function words. Other common features of this subject’s speech are the phonological reductions. Examples are “he is a” becoming /hi:zə/ and “me and my” becoming /mi:nmaɪ/ (elision). Upon completion of the activity, scrolling down to the bottom of the page and referring to the “scholarly comment” and “general comment” sections also directs attention to previously unnoticed features of speech that add to the discussion. One such example from the scholarly comment section is “the interview section has some examples of “uptalk” (raising the inflection at the end of sentences, so that statements become questions)”. Students are then asked

to find such examples. Finally, although there are many other suprasegmental features such as different varieties of connected speech, rhythm and tone, instruction in these aspects of speech prosody would be more appropriate in an advanced course in English phonology. Students then produce these reduced forms in English speaking practice activities.

Activity 2: Accent Awareness (Reception)

This activity is similar to Activity 1 above, except that the focus is on identifying and presenting on features of NNS accents, not suprasegmentals. It is done with individual speech samples of NNSs or by comparing different NNS speech samples. Students choose a NNS speech sample from either the Speech Accent Archive or IDEA and listen to it multiple times, taking note of the features that distinguish the speaker's accent. It is suggested that students have their own listening device (a smartphone is sufficient) and, if possible, earphones to reduce classroom noise. Having individual devices allows students to listen to the speech sample multiple times to identify features of the subject's speech. It is important to stress to students that this is an exercise in finding features of speech, not wrong pronunciation. As noted on the Speech Accent Archive site, the purpose of the archive is to "demonstrate that accents are systematic rather than merely mistaken speech" (cited online). Reference to the "scholarly comment" and "general comment" sections of IDEA or the "Generalizations" section of the speech accent archive assists students in identifying an accent's distinguishing features. Other questions that stimulate discussion include: *What features contribute to the speaker's intelligibility? What features negatively impact the speaker's intelligibility? What features make this accent different from the accent of your country?*

Activity 3: Shadow Reading (Production/Reception)

Due to the rapid pace of speech of many NS extemporaneous speech samples, those used for shadow reading may only serve to discourage students, if not carefully selected. However, when carefully chosen, these samples provide students with an effective method of actively practicing a variety of suprasegmental features. Information in the unscripted speech samples of IDEA, also with careful selection, are usually appropriate as they are mostly short monologues involving a subject's hometown, background and upbringing. As such they are not overly challenging in content. Shadow reading is a form of shadowing carried out with not only the voice for listening and imitating, but also with the script, in this case the orthographic transcription. Students listen while reading the transcription multiple times, first marking stress. During the second and third listens connected speech and intonation are marked. Finally, students practice reading through the transcription (with stress, intonation and connected speech marked) firstly with, and then without the IDEA recording.

Activity 4: NNS Interview (Reception)

To provide students with a real-life experience outside the classroom that incorporates NNS accommodation, students are instructed to conduct interviews with NNSs of English in their school community. Such an activity is more suited to intermediate or higher-level students who have the confidence to interact one on one with an interviewee. After initial instruction in how to conduct an interview and careful formulation of questions under a teacher's supervision, interviews are conducted by students, either in person or through video conferencing platforms. Possible topics for the interview could involve the interviewee's language learning experiences or experiences

living in a foreign country. Not only does the actual interview provide an opportunity for students to practically apply their receptive skills, but the post-interview transcription of the recorded interview offers an opportunity to listen to and analyse features of the interviewee's NNS language sample. The final stage of this activity requires the students to present to the class on both the content of the interview and the features of the interviewee's language.

Activity 5: Mirroring (Production)

Recently popularized by Tarone and Meyers (2018), mirroring is an effective means of improving not only awareness of suprasegmentals but also in providing students with an opportunity to produce suprasegmentals. The first step in this activity requires students to select a model or subject from which they will be required, in the final stage, to imitate or mirror both the actions and speech patterns of the subject. TED talks are ideal for selecting subjects because they feature highly skilled presenters, as proficient in their manner of speaking as they are in using suitable body language when presenting. Although self-selection of subjects is an important part of this project, teachers should take care that students choose appropriate models. NS models do not need to be insisted upon (Meyers' student chooses a Chinese media personality, Yang Lan), but NS subjects are usually more appropriate during this activity for the following reasons: (a) this avoids odd accent mismatches, e.g., a Japanese student perfectly mirroring an Indian accent (b) NS subjects are more popular with students in Japan and (c) NS models are generally richer in suprasegmental features to mirror and learn. After selection, students must go through a process of selecting a short segment of the presentation (about 7–10 sentences), carefully analyzing the speech and movement of the presenter taking careful notes on intonation, stress and other suprasegmental features, and then finally performing the short segment as closely as possible to the original, either live in the classroom or on video. Through this process of analysis and then production of language, students will then ideally incorporate features of another speaker's speech into part of their own repertoire. Readers are directed to the reference list for a YouTube workshop on mirroring.

Conclusion

Authentic materials are not only a rich source of suprasegmental features but also an excellent way to present the wide variety of NS and NNS Englishes that can enhance a learner's exposure to 'real' language. Although it has been argued that the difficulty of authentic materials can have a demotivating effect on students, when selected carefully, the many pedagogic and motivational benefits can easily outweigh the disadvantages with guided instruction. Focusing on raising awareness of the many rich suprasegmental features that are present in authentic materials creates learning opportunities that are often unavailable when using the more contrived language samples in textbooks. Production activities, that aim to improve suprasegmental use, and therefore intelligibility, deliver benefits that the less spontaneous didactic materials often fail to provide. In addition to increased exposure to suprasegmentals, exposure to authentic NNS Englishes not only inspire confidence and greater acceptance of NNS abilities but also familiarize English learners with a range of differing accents they are likely to encounter in real-life interactions. The materials outlined in this paper also provide students with an opportunity to learn more autonomously and with increased motivation.

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